

An Extended Review on Reversible Logic Gates and their Implementation

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Abstract : In recent years, reversible logic circuits have applications in the emerging field of digital signal processing, computer graphics and cryptography. They are also a fundamental requirement in the field of quantum computation. We have investigated that the purposes of designing reversible logic are to decrease the number of reversible gates, garbage outputs, constant inputs, quantum cost, area, power, delay and hardware complexity of the reversible circuits. This paper provides some reversible logic gates, which can be used in designing more complex systems having reversible circuits and can execute more complicated operations using quantum computers. The reversible circuits form the basic building blocks of quantum computers as all quantum operations are inherently reversible. This paper presents the data relating to the reversible gates which helps in designing complex circuits.

Keywords - Constant Input, Delay, Garbage Output, Quantum Cost, Reversible Gate, Reversible Logic.

I. INTRODUCTION

Reversible logic computing has received significant research attention recently [1]. Applications of the reversible circuits can be found in the emerging fields of the quantum computation, low-power computation and digital signal processing. Conventional irreversible logic circuits necessarily dissipate energy due to the erasure of information [2-3]. But reversible computation can be performed with arbitrarily small energy dissipation. Bennett showed that the power dissipation in reversible logic computing is zero under ideal physical circumstances [3].

Quantum computing is also a rapidly emerging area [4]. Since quantum logic operations are inherently reversible, studying the testing of reversible circuits may assist in the development of physical realizations of quantum gates based on trapped ion technology, photons and non-linear optical media, cavity-quantum electro-dynamic devices, spin in semiconductors etc.

In quantum computing, by considering the need of reversible gates, a literature survey has been done and the mostly available reversible logic gates are presented in [5]. For designing complex circuits using reversible gates, a literature survey has been done and the remaining reversible logic gates which are not presented in [5] are presented in this paper.

II. BASIC DEFINITIONS OF REVERSIBLE LOGIC

In this section, we will show some basic definitions pertaining to reversible logic synthesis.

1. Reversible Function

The multiple output Boolean Function $F(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ of n Boolean variables is called reversible if:

- i. The number of outputs is equal to the number of inputs,
- ii. Any output pattern has a unique pre-image.

In other words, the functions which perform permutations of the set of input vectors are referred to as reversible functions [6].

2. Reversible Logic Gate

Reversible logic has unique mapping between input and output bit pattern. A unit logic entity is represented as gate. The gates or circuits that do not lose information are called reversible [3] gates or circuits.

Definition 1: A reversible circuit is such a circuit in which the number of input and the number of output is equal. And of course, there is one-to-one mapping between input and output vectors.

Let's consider the gate shown in Fig. 1. According to the definition, the gate is a reversible gate, because it has k number of inputs and k number of outputs and the gate is known as $k \times k$ Reversible Gate. Without the NOT gate, classical logic gates are called irreversible, since they cannot determine the input vector states from the output vector states uniquely.

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Example 1: There can be any number of dimensions for a reversible gate, but lower dimension is always preferable for designing efficient circuits. The popular reversible gates are Feynman Gate (FG) [7], Toffoli Gate (TG) [8], Peres Gate (PG) [9], Fredkin Gate (FRG) [10], Feynman Double Gate (F2G) [11] and New Fault Tolerant (NFT) [12] which are shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1. A $k \times k$ Reversible Gate.

Fig. 2. Popular Reversible Gates.

3. Garbage Outputs

Every gate's output that is not used as input to other gate or as a primary output is called garbage output. The unutilized outputs from a gate are called *garbage*. Heavy price is paid off for every garbage output. So, it should always keep in mind that, the less number of garbage is quite good for any circuit design.

Example 2: In Fig. 3, the garbage bit of a gate is shown. Here, **A** is the garbage bit.

Fig. 3. Garbage Bit.

4. Constant Inputs

Constant inputs are the inputs of a reversible gate (or circuit) that are either set to 0 or 1.

Example 3: If we want the complement of the input A from Fig. 3, then we set B to 1 and we get $Q = A'$.

5. Quantum Cost

Quantum theory is a gigantic research field deeply related to crucial applications as DNA technologies, nanotechnologies and optical computing etc. Reversible quantum logic plays an important role in quantum computing.

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Definition 2: The quantum cost of a circuit is the total number of 2×2 quantum primitives are used to realize corresponding quantum circuit. Basically, the quantum primitives are matrix operations, which are applied on qubits state.

Example 4: The cost of all 2×2 gates are same and it is 1 and 0 for 1×1 [13]. Every circuit can be constructed from those 1×1 and 2×2 quantum primitives and the cost of circuit is the total sum of used 2×2 gates [14].

6. Delay

The delay of a logic circuit is the maximum number of gates in a path from any input line to any output line. The definition is based on two assumptions: (i) Each gate performs computation in one unit time and (ii) all inputs to the circuit are available before the computation begins. In this paper, we used the logical depth as measure of the delay proposed by Mohammadi and Eshghi [15].

Example 5: The delay of each 1×1 and 2×2 reversible gate is taken as unit delay 1. Any 3×3 reversible gate can be designed from 1×1 reversible gates and 2×2 reversible gates, such as CNOT gate, Controlled-V and Controlled-V+ gates (V is a square-root-of NOT gate and V+ is its hermitian). Thus, the delay of a 3×3 reversible gate can be computed by calculating its logical depth when it is designed from smaller 1×1 and 2×2 reversible gates.

7. Power

This refers to the total power dissipated during logical operation in entire design by using CMOS logic [16].

8. Flexibility

This refers to the universality of a reversible logic gate in realizing more functions [17].

9. Hardware Complexity

Definition 3: Hardware Complexity of a circuit is the total logical operation performed by the circuit. Total logical calculation is the count of the Ex-OR (α), AND (β) and NOT (δ) in the output expressions [18].

Example 6: The hardware complexity of a Peres gate is $2\alpha + \beta$.

10. Quantum Gate Calculation Complexity

Definition 4: The quantum gate calculation complexity refers to the number of quantum gates used to synthesize the given circuit, where ρ , σ and Ω are the NOT, CNOT and Controlled-V (Controlled-V⁺) quantum gate calculation complexities, respectively.

Example 7: The quantum gate calculation complexity of a Peres gate is $\sigma + 3\Omega$.

11. Design Constraints for Reversible Logic Circuits

The following are the important design constraints for reversible logic circuits.

- Reversible logic gates do not allow fan-outs.
- The reversible logic circuits should have minimum number of reversible gates.
- Reversible logic circuits should have minimum quantum cost.
- The design can be optimized so as to produce minimum number of garbage outputs.
- The reversible logic circuits must use minimum number of constant inputs.
- The reversible logic circuits must use a minimum logic depth or gate levels.
- Reversible logic circuits should have minimum power.
- The reversible logic circuits must use minimum hardware complexity and minimum quantum gate calculation complexity.

III. REVERSIBLE LOGIC GATES

At present there exist many reversible gates in the literature. Some of the reversible gates are shown in [5]. In this paper, we try to show other reversible gates which are not shown in [5] and may help researchers for further researches. The reversible logic gates are given below.

1. TS-3 Gate

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TS-3 gate is also known as Thapliyal gate [19]. It is a 3×3 reversible gate. The TS-3 gate can be described as: $I_V = (A, B, C)$; $O_V = (A, B, A \oplus B \oplus C)$, where I_V and O_V are input and output vectors respectively. Quantum cost of TS-3 gate is two [20]. Fig. 4 shows a 3×3 TS-3 gate and its quantum representation.

Fig. 4. TS-3 Gate.

2. MNFT Gate

MNFT gate is also known as Modified New Fault Tolerant gate [21]. It is a 3×3 reversible gate. The MNFT gate can be described as: $I_V = (A, B, C)$; $O_V = ((A \oplus B)C \oplus A, A \oplus B, (A \oplus B)C \oplus A \oplus C)$, where I_V and O_V are input and output vectors respectively. Quantum cost of MNFT gate is five [21]. Fig. 5 shows a 3×3 MNFT gate and its quantum representation.

Fig. 5. MNFT Gate.

3. SAM Gate

SAM gate is also known as Selim Al Mamun gate [22]. It is a 3×3 reversible gate. The SAM gate can be described as: $I_V = (A, B, C)$; $O_V = (A', A'B \oplus AC', A'C \oplus AB)$, where I_V and O_V are input and output vectors respectively. Quantum cost of SAM gate is five [22]. Fig. 6 shows a 3×3 SAM gate and its quantum representation.

Fig. 6. SAM Gate.

4. SRK Gate

SRK gate is also known as Sadia Rahman gate [20]. It is a 3×3 reversible gate. The SRK gate can be described as: $I_V = (A, B, C)$; $O_V = (A', A \oplus B \oplus C, A'C \oplus AB)$, where I_V and O_V are input and output vectors respectively. Quantum cost of SRK gate is four [23]. Fig. 7 shows a 3×3 SRK gate and its quantum representation.

Fig. 7. SRK Gate.

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5. IG Gate

IG gate is also known as Islam gate [24]. It is a 4×4 reversible gate. The IG gate can be described as: $I_V = (A, B, C, D)$; $O_V = (A, A \oplus B, AB \oplus C, BD \oplus B'(A \oplus D))$, where I_V and O_V are input and output vectors respectively. Quantum cost of IG gate is seven [24]. Fig. 8 shows a 4×4 IG gate and its quantum representation.

Fig. 8. IG Gate.

6. MIG Gate

MIG gate is also known as Modified Islam gate [25]. It is a 4×4 reversible gate. The MIG gate can be described as: $I_V = (A, B, C, D)$; $O_V = (A, A \oplus B, AB \oplus C, AB' \oplus D)$, where I_V and O_V are input and output vectors respectively. Quantum cost of MIG gate is seven [25]. Fig. 9 shows a 4×4 MIG gate and its quantum representation.

Fig. 9. MIG Gate.

7. HNFG Gate

HNFG gate is a 4×4 reversible gate [26]. The HNFG gate can be described as: $I_V = (A, B, C, D)$; $O_V = (A, A \oplus C, B, B \oplus D)$, where I_V and O_V are input and output vectors respectively. Quantum cost of HNFG gate is two which is illustrated in [27]. Fig. 10 shows a 4×4 HNFG gate.

Fig. 10. HNFG Gate.

8. RR Gate

RR gate is also known as Ravi Ranjith gate [28]. It is a 4×4 reversible gate. The RR gate can be described as: $I_V = (A, B, C, D)$; $O_V = (B, B'C + BD, B'C + BD \oplus A, C \oplus D)$, where I_V and O_V are input and output vectors respectively. Quantum cost of RR gate is six which is illustrated in [28]. Fig. 11 shows a 4×4 RR gate.

Fig. 11. RR Gate.

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9. PPHCG Gate

PPHCG gate is known as Parity Preserving HC gate. It is a 4×4 reversible gate [29]. The PPHCG gate can be described as: $I_V = (A, B, C, D)$; $O_V = (B \oplus C \oplus D, A \oplus B \oplus C, A \oplus B \oplus D, A \oplus C \oplus D)$, where I_V and O_V are input and output vectors respectively. Quantum cost of PPHCG gate is six which is illustrated in [29]. Fig. 12 shows a 4×4 PPHCG gate.

Fig. 12. PPHCG Gate.

10. PFAG Gate

PFAG gate is also known as Peres Full Adder Gate [30]. It is a 4×4 reversible gate. The PFAG gate can be described as: $I_V = (A, B, C, D)$; $O_V = (A, A \oplus B, A \oplus B \oplus C, (A \oplus B)C \oplus AB \oplus D)$, where I_V and O_V are input and output vectors respectively. Quantum cost of PFAG gate is eight which is illustrated in [30]. Fig. 13 shows a 4×4 PFAG gate.

Fig. 13. PFAG Gate.

11. SG Gate

SG gate is also known as Sayem gate [31]. It is a 4×4 reversible gate. The SG gate can be described as: $I_V = (A, B, C, D)$; $O_V = (A, A'B \oplus AC, A'B \oplus AC \oplus D, AB \oplus A'C \oplus D)$, where I_V and O_V are input and output vectors respectively. Quantum cost of SG gate is not shown in the literature till now. Fig. 14 shows a 4×4 SG gate.

Fig. 14. SG Gate.

12. BME Gate

BME gate is a 4×4 reversible gate [32]. The BME gate can be described as: $I_V = (A, B, C, D)$; $O_V = (A, AB \oplus C, AD \oplus C, A'B \oplus C \oplus D)$, where I_V and O_V are input and output vectors respectively. Quantum cost of BME gate is five [32]. Fig. 15 shows a 4×4 BME gate.

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Fig. 15. BME Gate.

13. PAREEK Gate

PAREEK gate is a 4×4 reversible gate [33]. The PAREEK gate can be described as: $I_V = (A, B, C, D)$; $O_V = (A, A'B \oplus AD, A'B \oplus AD \oplus C, B \oplus D)$, where I_V and O_V are input and output vectors respectively. Quantum cost of PAREEK gate is seven which is illustrated in [33]. Fig. 16 shows a 4×4 PAREEK gate.

Fig. 16. PAREEK Gate.

14. PPPG Gate

PPPG gate is a 5×5 reversible gate [34]. The PPPG gate can be described as: $I_V = (A, B, C, D, E)$; $O_V = (A, A'C' \oplus B', (A'C' \oplus B') \oplus D, (A'C' \oplus B')D \oplus (AB \oplus C), BE(A+D) + A'D(C \oplus E) + B'D(A+E))$, where I_V and O_V are input and output vectors respectively. Quantum cost of PPPG gate is not shown in the literature till now. Fig. 17 shows a 5×5 PPPG gate.

Fig. 17. PPPG Gate.

15. F2PG Gate

F2PG gate is a 5×5 reversible gate [34]. The PPPG gate can be described as: $I_V = (A, B, C, D, E)$; $O_V = (A, A'C' \oplus B', (A'C' \oplus B') \oplus D, (A'C' \oplus B')D \oplus (AB \oplus C), BE(A+D) + A'D(C \oplus E) + B'D(A+E))$, where I_V and O_V are input and output vectors respectively. Quantum cost of PPPG gate is not shown in the literature till now. Fig. 17 shows a 5×5 PPPG gate.

Fig. 18. F2PG Gate.

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16. FTRG Gate

FTRG gate is also known as Fault Tolerant Reversible gate [35]. It is a 5×5 reversible gate. The FTRG gate can be described as: $I_V = (A, B, C, D, E)$; $O_V = (A \oplus B \oplus C, BC + ((B+C).(A \oplus D)), AB + AD, B'C + (B+C).(A \oplus B), A'E' + A(D \oplus E \oplus B))$, where I_V and O_V are input and output vectors respectively. Quantum cost of FTRG gate is not shown in the literature till now. Fig. 19 shows a 5×5 FTRG gate.

Fig. 19. FTRG Gate.

17. RSG Gate

RSG gate is a 5×5 reversible gate [36]. The RSG gate can be described as: $I_V = (A, B, C, D, E)$; $O_V = (A, B, C, AB \oplus D, AC \oplus E)$, where I_V and O_V are input and output vectors respectively. Quantum cost of RSG gate is ten which is illustrated in [36]. Fig. 20 shows a 5×5 RSG gate.

Fig. 20. RSG Gate.

18. BVPPG Gate

BVPPG gate is a 5×5 reversible gate [37]. The BVPPG gate can be described as: $I_V = (A, B, C, D, E)$; $O_V = (A, B, AB \oplus C, D, AD \oplus E)$, where I_V and O_V are input and output vectors respectively. Quantum cost of BVPPG gate is ten which is illustrated in [37]. Fig. 21 shows a 5×5 BVPPG gate.

Fig. 21. BVPPG Gate.

19. BBCDC Gate

BBCDC gate is also known as Binary to BCD Conversion gate [38]. It is a 5×5 reversible gate. The BBCDC gate can be described as: $I_V = (A, B, C, D, E)$; $O_V = (A, BD'E' \oplus B'(CD \oplus E), B'E \oplus C(B \oplus D'), BE \oplus B'C'D, E \oplus D(B \oplus C))$, where I_V and O_V are input and output vectors respectively. Quantum cost of BBCDC gate is not shown in the literature till now. Fig. 22 shows a 5×5 BBCDC gate.

Fig. 22. BBCDC Gate.

20. MPS Gate

MPS gate is a 5×5 reversible gate [39]. The MPS gate can be described as: $I_V = (A, B, C, D, E)$; $O_V = (AB'+A'BC+BC'(A\oplus D), A(C+B)+C'(AB'D+A'BD'), A'C(B'+BE)+AC'D'+AC(B+D), BC(A\oplus D)'+B'(A\oplus D)+ABC', E)$, where I_V and O_V are input and output vectors respectively. Quantum cost of MPS gate is not shown in the literature till now. Fig. 23 shows a 5×5 MPS gate.

Fig. 23. MPS Gate.

21. HASFT Gate

HASFT gate is a 5×5 reversible gate [40]. The HASFT gate can be described as: $I_V = (A, B, C, D, E)$; $O_V = (A, D\oplus B(A\oplus C), B\oplus C, D\oplus B(A\oplus C)', B\oplus D\oplus E)$, where I_V and O_V are input and output vectors respectively. Quantum cost of HASFT gate is ten which is illustrated in [40]. Fig. 24 shows a 5×5 HASFT gate.

Fig. 24. HASFT Gate.

22. FASFT Gate

FASFT gate is a 5×5 reversible gate [40]. The FASFT gate can be described as: $I_V = (A, B, C, D, E)$; $O_V = (A, B, A\oplus B\oplus C, A(B\oplus C)\oplus BC\oplus D, A(B\oplus C)'\oplus BC'\oplus E)$, where I_V and O_V are input and output vectors respectively. Quantum cost of FASFT gate is ten which is illustrated in [40]. Fig. 25 shows a 5×5 FASFT gate.

Fig. 25. FASFT Gate.

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IV. CONCLUSION

The reversible circuits form the basic building block of quantum computers. This paper presents the reversible gates which are not shown in [5] and which are gathered from the literature till now. This paper helps researches/designers in designing higher complex computing circuits using reversible gates. This paper can further be extended towards quantum computing, low power CMOS, nanotechnology, quantum dot cellular automata etc.

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